

Improved Nonparametric Density Estimation Using Additive Kernel Estimators

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work in this thesis is my own has been in accordance with generally accepted scientific bases.

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ABSTRACT

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One way of improving the rate of convergent of classical kernel estimator is to use higher r -order kernel function. In this thesis suggests a new "additive kernel estimator" to estimate $f(x)$, the proposed estimator are simple and interpretable as the higher r -order estimator. The asymptotic properties of the proposed estimator are derived and formula for the smoothing parameter is given based on minimizing the asymptotic mean square error (AMSE), and some important case of this estimator are studied. Theoretical and practical result show the good potential properties of the proposed estimator over the higher r -order kernel estimator.

Keyword:

Kernel method, higher r -order kernel estimator, smoothing parameter, bias rate of convergence.

ملخص

الكايد ، سامي فالح "مقدر النواة التجميعي لاقتران الكثافة الاحتمالية" رسالة ماجستير بجامعة اليرموك، 2011 (المشرف: الدكتور عمر محمد اعدوس).

احدى طرق تحسين نسبة التقارب لتقدير النواة الاعتيادي هي استخدام تقدير النواة الاسي. وفي هذه الاطروحة نقترح مقدر نواة تجميعي جديد لتقدير مقدر النواة الاعتيادي حيث يمتاز ببساطته وسهولة التعامل معه كما هو الحال في مقدر النواة الاسي.

وعلاوة على ذلك ، فقد تم اشتقاق خصائص التقارب لمقدر النواة الجديد ومقدر النواة الاسي متضمنتاً ايضاً اشتقاقاً لمعلمة التجانس وذلك بالاعتماد على تقليل القيمة التقريبية لمعدل تربيع الخطأ. بالاضافة الى دراسة بعض الحالات المهمة لهذا المقدر الجديد.

وقد اظهرت النتائج النظرية والعملية لمقدر النواة الجديد مميزات افضل من مقدر النواة الاسي.

الكلمات المفتاحية:

طريقة النواة ، اقتران النواة الاسي ، معلمة التجانس ، معدل التحيز للتقارب.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

There are two approaches to determine the unknown probability density function (*pdf*) $f(x)$ for a random sample X_1, \dots, X_n . One can either choose the parametric approach, which requires the assumption that the random sample belongs to a known parametric family of distributions with unknown parameter(s). Then the unknown parameter(s) are estimated based on a random sample X_1, \dots, X_n . An obvious pitfall of the parametric approach is that important data structure can be masked when there is no previous knowledge of the sample to assist in the choice of the parametric family of distributions. Alternatively, we can determine the *pdf* by using the nonparametric approach, which requires no assumptions about the form of density for the random sample. Thus, a nonparametric approach is a good choice to estimate the unknown *pdf* $f(x)$.

The most popular non parametric method in density estimation is called “kernel density estimation”. The estimator obtained by using this method will be called as an “ordinary kernel density estimator”,

1.2 Classical Kernel Method

Let X_1, \dots, X_n be a random sample from a continuous, univariate pdf $f(x)$. The nonparametric ordinary kernel density estimator of $f(x)$ is (Silverman, 1986).

$$\hat{f}(x) = (nh)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n K_{(2)}\{(x - X_i)/h\} \quad (1.1)$$

where $K_{(2)}$ is called the kernel function (second-order kernel function) and h is a positive real number, called the bandwidth or the smoothing parameter. The kernel function $K_{(2)}$ is assumed to be symmetric function satisfying

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K_{(2)}(u)du = 1, \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} uK_{(2)}(u)du = 0, \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2K_{(2)}(u)du = k_2 \neq 0 < \infty \quad (1.2)$$

Let $h \rightarrow 0$ and $nh \rightarrow \infty$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, then under these assumptions, the expected value of $\hat{f}(x)$ is (Silverman, 1986)

$$E\hat{f}(x) = f(x) + \frac{1}{2}h^2\mu_2(K_{(2)})f''(x) + o(h^2). \quad (1.3)$$

Which gives,

$$bias(\hat{f}(x)) = \frac{1}{2}h^2\mu_2(K_{(2)})f''(x) + o(h^2) \quad , \quad (1.4)$$

where $\mu_2(K_{(2)}) = \int z^2 K_{(2)}(z)dz$. According to Silverman (1986), the variance of $\hat{f}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} var\{\hat{f}(x)\} &= (nh)^{-1} \int K_{(2)}^2(z)f(x - hz)dz \\ &= (nh)^{-1}R(K_{(2)})f(x) + o\{(nh)^{-1}\} \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

where $R(g) = \int g^2(x) dx$. Therefore, the mean square error (MSE) of $\hat{f}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{MSE}(\hat{f}(x)) &= E(\hat{f}(x) - f(x))^2 \\
&= \text{Var}(\hat{f}(x)) + (E\hat{f}(x) - f(x))^2 \\
&= (nh)^{-1}R(K_{(2)})f(x) + \frac{1}{4}h^4\mu_2(K_{(2)})^2f''(x)^2 + o\{(nh)^{-1} \\
&\quad + h^4\}. \tag{1.6}
\end{aligned}$$

The MSE combines the variance and the squared bias of $\hat{f}(x)$ at a fixed point x to measure the quality of $\hat{f}(x)$. The mean integrated squared error (MISE) is another global measure which used to measure the quality of $\hat{f}(x)$ over the entire real line. It is simply defined by (Silverman, 1986):

$$\text{MISE} = \int \text{MSE}(\hat{f}(x)) dx.$$

Therefore the asymptotic mean integrated square error (AMISE) of $\hat{f}(x)$ is (Wand and Jones, 1995)

$$\text{AMISE}\{\hat{f}(x)\} = (nh)^{-1}R(K_{(2)}) + \frac{1}{4}h^4\mu_2(K_{(2)})^2R(f''). \tag{1.7}$$

1.3 Smoothing Parameter Selection

The choice of the bandwidth h in the kernel density estimator is very important because the value of the bandwidth plays a vital role in the accuracy of the kernel density estimator (Wand and Jones 1995). As we can see from (1.4) and (1.5), if the bandwidth h is chosen too large, then the bias of $\hat{f}(x)$ increases and the

variance decreases. On the other hand, if the bandwidth is too small, then the bias of $\hat{f}(x)$ decreases and the variance increases. Usually, the bandwidth is chosen by finding the value of h that minimizes the AMISE. This value of h is known as the optimal bandwidth with respect to AMISE, which is given by Jeter (2005),

$$h = \left[\frac{R(K(z))}{\mu_2(K(z))^2 R(f'')n} \right]^{1/5}. \quad (1.8)$$

The value of h is obtained by considering the AMISE in (1.7) as a function of h (say $d(h)$), differentiate $d(h)$ with respect to h and equating to zero, then solve the resulting equation with respect to h to obtain the rule of h in (1.8) (Raykar and Duraiswami, 2005).

Formula (1.8) demonstrates that h approaches to zero (when n approaches to infinity) but at a rate slower than n^{-1} .

1.4 Kernel Function

The selection of kernel function K is discussed in Silverman (1986). He reported that all functions $K(z)$ that satisfy $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(z)dz = 1$, $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} z K(z)dz = 0$ & $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} z^2 K(z)dz \neq 0 < \infty$ perform about the same as each other in estimating $f(x)$. For example, the following functions are candidate as kernel function:

(a) $K(z) = \frac{1}{2}$, $|z| < 1$, (Rectangular kernel)

$$(b) K(z) = \frac{3}{4} \left(1 - \frac{1}{5}z^2\right) / \sqrt{5} \quad , |z| < \sqrt{5} \quad , (\text{Epanechnikov kernel})$$

$$(c) K(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2n}} e^{-z^2/2} \quad , -\infty < z < \infty \quad , (\text{Gaussian kernel})$$

Usually, the kernel function K is chosen to be a unimodal and symmetric density to yield unbiased estimates by using a symmetric distribution of the weights on both sides of the point of estimate. However, the selection of h is more effect on the performance of $\hat{f}(x; h, n)$ rather than K (Ali, 1998).

1.5 Literature Review

The applications of nonparametric density estimation method were increasing in the recent years and also more researchers have interesting on this density estimation method. The kernel density estimation method simplifies them self on the nonparametric density estimation methods to estimate $f(x)$. some recent book on kernel it's density estimation for statistic and datd analysis by silverman (1986).Kernel smoothing by Wand M.P. and Jones M.C.(1995). Wand M.P. and Schucany W.R. (1990) derived a class of higher order kernel.

In particular high-order finite-differences solutions (Claerbout 1985) and methods from the pseudo-screen family (Huang, Fehler and Wu 1999) and Fourier finite differences family (Ristow and Ruhl 1994; Biondi 2002).

It is well known (Parzen 1962; Pagan and Ullah 1999; Fan and Yao 2003) that if f has its r th derivative bounded and continuous at x an interior point in the support

off and the kernel is of order r , that is, K satisfies $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} K(t)t^j dt = 0$ for $j = 1, \dots, r - 1$ then $\text{Bias}(f_R(x)) = O(hr^n)$. Bias reduction through higher order kernels (Granovsky and Müller 1991; Jones and Foster 1993) can be inconvenient in that for $r > 2$, K can no longer be nonnegative everywhere and therefore $f_R(x)$ may be negative. There exist other approaches to bias reduction in density estimation (Jones, Linton, and Nielsen 1995; DiMarzio and Taylor 2004) but the asymptotic properties of these estimators have not been fully developed.

Investigated some possibilities for improvements of kernel density estimates using line transect sampling and he proposed two nonparametric estimators Eidous (2009).

Kernel methods and its adaptation are among the most important nonparametric techniques for estimating probability density functions, offering a flexible and intuitive approach without relying on strict parametric assumptions. The classical kernel estimator has been widely applied in various fields and continues to be an essential tool for density estimation. However, improving its performance—particularly the rate of convergence and bias reduction—remains an active area of research.

To address the limitations of classical kernel estimators, several enhancements have been proposed over the years. One common approach is the use of higher-

order kernel functions, which can reduce bias and improve the asymptotic mean square error (AMSE). While effective, higher-order estimators often involve complex kernel structures and may lack interpretability.

Significant contributions to kernel-based methods have been made in the context of line transect sampling and wildlife abundance estimation. For instance, Chen (1996), Mack and Quang (1998), and

Eidous (2005d) applied kernel estimators in analyzing line transect data. Eidous (2003, 2004a, 2004b) introduced histogram and kernel-based techniques to improve density estimation, followed by parametric models (Eidous, 2004c and Eidous and Al-Masri, 2006), polygon estimators, and bias-corrected histograms (Eidous, 2005a, 2005b). Further developments included enhanced kernel estimators (Eidous, 2005c, 2005d, 2006, 2009, 2010, 2011a), as well as relaxations of assumptions like the shoulder condition (Eidous, 2011b, 2012a, 2012b) and improved bandwidth selection techniques (Eidous, Marie & Al-Haj Ibrahim, 2010).

In addition, collaborative research has led to enriched models, such as those involving weighted detection functions (Ababneh & Eidous, 2012), entropy-based goodness-of-fit tests (Baklizi & Eidous, 2006, 2008, 2009 and Eidous and Baklizi, 2004), and double kernel methods (Eidous & Alshakhatreh, 2011a, 2011b). These

studies have played a crucial role in refining kernel-based estimators and extending their application to practical problems in ecology and beyond.

Motivated by the need for both improved accuracy and interpretability, this thesis proposes a new additive kernel estimator for estimating the probability density function $f(x)$. The proposed estimator retains the simplicity of the classical kernel method while exhibiting desirable asymptotic properties, similar to or better than those of higher-order kernel estimators. We derive the theoretical properties of the estimator, including its asymptotic bias and variance, and provide a formula for the optimal smoothing parameter based on minimizing the AMSE. Several important cases are explored, and empirical results demonstrate the estimator's strong potential, offering an attractive alternative to existing higher-order kernel approaches.

1.6 Thesis Objectives

The main objective of this research is to propose a new kernel estimator for the *pdf* $f(x)$ and to investigate its asymptotic properties. The proposed estimator is denoted by $\tilde{f}(x)$ and is given by Formula (2.9). In particular we are aiming to

- (1) Derive the asymptotic mean and the asymptotic variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$.
- (2) Derive a rule for the optimal value of the smoothing parameter b of $\tilde{f}(x)$.

(3) Explore the relationship between the asymptotic properties of $\tilde{f}(x)$ and that of the higher-order kernel estimator, which is given by Formula (2.2).

(4) Make a mathematical comparison between the properties of $\tilde{f}(x)$ and that of the higher-order kernel estimator (2.2). In this case, particular cases are considered and studied.

1.7 Organization of the Thesis

According to our objectives, this thesis is organized as the following:

In Chapter One, we presented the classical kernel estimator of $f(x)$ together with some related topics. Chapter Two describes the higher-order kernel estimator and the proposed estimator of $f(x)$. The asymptotic statistical properties (the bias, the variance and the mean square error, MSE) of both estimators are also presented in this chapter .

A mathematical comparison study between the asymptotic properties of the higher order kernel density estimator and the proposed estimator is presented in Chapter Three. The conclusions of the study and the suggestions for further research are given in Chapter Four.

CHAPTER TWO

HIGHER-ORDER KERNEL AND PROPOSED ESTIMATOR

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we describe the higher-order kernel estimator of $f(x)$ and its asymptotic properties. The proposed estimator is also presented. Its asymptotic properties are derived and a formula for the optimal smoothing parameter of the proposed estimator is given. The relationship between the properties of two estimators are also derived in the final section of this chapter.

2.2 Higher-Order Kernel Density Estimator

One way of improving the performance of ordinary kernel estimator (1.1) is to use higher-order kernel function. The function $K_{(2)}$ in (1.1) is called second order kernel function. Let $\mu_j(K_{(r)}) = \int Z^j K_{(r)}(z) dz$, then the second-order kernel, $K_{(2)}$ requires $\mu_0(K_{(2)}) = 1$, $\mu_1(K_{(2)}) = 0$, and $\mu_2(K_{(2)}) = k_2 \neq 0 < \infty$, to ensure that the bias of estimator (1.1) has a rate of convergence $O(h^2)$, while the convergence rate of the variance is $O(nh)^{-1}$.

To improve the bias convergence rate of estimator (1.1), one can construct higher-order kernels (Wand and Jones, 1995). Let $K_{(r)}$ be the r^{th} -order kernel assumed to be symmetric (even) function, then $K_{(r)}$ is defined to have

$$\begin{cases} \mu_0(K_{(r)}) = 1 \\ \mu_j(K_{(r)}) = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r-1 \quad . \\ \mu_r(K_{(r)}) = k_r \neq 0 < \infty \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

For example, the fourth-order kernel ($r = 4$) is the kernel function $K_{(4)}$ that should be satisfying $\mu_0(K_{(4)}) = 1$, $\mu_1(K_{(4)}) = \mu_2(K_{(4)}) = \mu_3(K_{(4)}) = 0$ and $\mu_4(K_{(4)}) = k_4 \neq 0 < \infty$.

Wand and Jones (1995) gave a rule that can be adopted to construct higher-order kernels as the following:

Let $\phi(x)$ be the standard normal pdf and take $K_{(2)}(x) = \phi(x)$, then the r^{th} -order kernel, $K_{(r)}$ is obtained by using:

$$K_{(r)}(x) = \frac{3}{2}K_{(r-2)}(x) + \frac{1}{2}xK'_{(r-2)}(x) \quad , \quad r = 4, 6, 8, \dots$$

For example, the fourth-order kernel, $K_{(4)}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} K_{(4)}(x) &= \frac{3}{2}K_{(2)}(x) + \frac{1}{2}xK'_{(2)}(x) \\ &= \frac{3}{2}\phi(x) + \frac{1}{2}x\phi'(x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{3}{2} \phi(x) - \frac{1}{2} x^2 \phi(x) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \phi(x)(3 - x^2).
\end{aligned}$$

Wand and Schucany (1990) gave a class of higher-order kernels that satisfies condition (2.1). They derived the following rule to construct $K_{(r)}(x)$ based on the Gaussian kernel function

$$K_{(r)}(x) = \frac{(-1)^{r/2} \phi^{(r-1)}(x)}{2^{r/2-1} (r/2 - 1)! x} \quad r = 2, 4, 6, \dots$$

where $\phi(x)$ is the standard normal distribution and $\phi^{(m)}(x)$ is the m^{th} derivative of $\phi(x)$. The first five even-order kernels are given in Table (2.1), which are taken from Wand and Schucany (1990). In addition, we added the value of $R(K_{(r)})$ of the corresponding even-order kernel and the rate of convergence for the corresponding bias.

Jones and foster (1993) demonstrated that the higher-order kernel ($r = 4, 6, \dots$) may take some negative terms and the density estimator based on them may be negative, especially in areas where the data are sparse , but this might be tolerated if improved bias ensues .

r	$K_{(r)}$	$R[K_{(r)}]$	bias rate of convergence
2	$\phi(x)$	0.2821	$O(h^{*2})$
4	$\frac{1}{2}(3 - x^2)\phi(x)$	0.4760	$O(h^{*4})$
6	$\frac{1}{8}(15 - 10x^2 + x^4)\phi(x)$	0.6240	$O(h^{*6})$
8	$\frac{1}{48}(105 - 105x^2 + 21x^4 - x^6)\phi(x)$	0.7479	$O(h^{*8})$
10	$\frac{1}{384}(945 - 1260x^2 + 378x^4 - 36x^6 + x^8)\phi(x)$	0.8565	$O(h^{*10})$

Table (2.1): Gaussian-kernel of order 2,4,6,8 and 10 (Wand and Schucany, 1990)

The question arises here is; why r takes only even values? The answer of this question can be illustrated as the following:

Because $K_{(r)}$ is assumed to be symmetric (even) function then $\mu_j(K_{(r)}) = 0, \forall j = 1, 3, 5, \dots$. Therefore, if one try to obtain $O(h^{*r})$ bias and if r is an odd value, then he obtained automatically $O(h^{*(r+1)})$. More clearing picture can be detected by inspecting the bias of $\hat{f}^*(x)$ in the next section.

2.2.1 The Expected Value and the Bias of $\hat{f}^*(x)$

Let X_1, \dots, X_n be a random sample from a continuous *pdf* $f(x)$ and assume that the r^{th} -order kernel that satisfies condition (2.1) is obtained, then the r^{th} -order kernel estimator of $f(x)$ is

$$\hat{f}^*(x) = (nh^*)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n K_{(r)}\{(x - X_i)/h^*\}, -\infty < x < \infty. \quad (2.2)$$

Under the assumption the r^{th} -order derivatives of $f(x)$ are continuous, Wand and Jones (1995) derived the expected value of $\hat{f}^*(x)$, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} E\hat{f}^*(x) &= \int K_{(r)}(z) \sum_{l=0}^r (-h^*z)^l (l!)^{-1} f^{(l)}(x) dz + o(h^{*r}) \\ &= f(x) - h^* f^{(1)}(x) \mu_1(K_{(r)}) + \frac{h^{*2}}{2} f^{(2)}(x) \mu_2(K_{(r)}) + \dots + \\ &\quad (-1)^r \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!} \right\} h^{*r} f^{(r)}(x) + o(h^{*r}). \end{aligned}$$

$$= f(x) + (-1)^r \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K(r))}{r!} \right\} h^{*r} f^{(r)}(x) + o(h^{*r}). \quad (2.3)$$

Therefore, the bias of $\hat{f}^*(x)$ is

$$\text{Bias } \hat{f}^*(x) = E\hat{f}^*(x) - f(x).$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (-1)^r \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K(r))}{r!} \right\} h^{*r} f^{(r)}(x) + o(h^{*r}) \\ &= Q_r h^{*r} f^{(r)}(x) + o(h^{*r}), \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

which indicates that the convergence rate of the bias of $\hat{f}^*(x)$ is $O(h^{*r})$. The

values of $Q_r = (-1)^r \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K(r))}{r!} \right\}$ for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are given in Table (2.2).

2.2.2 The Variance of $\hat{f}^*(x)$

The variance of $\hat{f}^*(x)$ is

$$\text{Var}(\hat{f}^*(x)) =$$

$$\text{Var}\{(nh)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n K\{(x - X_i)/h^*\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{nh^{*2}} E[K\{(x - X)/h^*\}]^2 - \frac{1}{nh^2} [EK\{(x - X)/h^*\}]^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{nh^*} f(x)R[K_{(r)}] + o(n^{-1}), \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

where $R(g) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g^2(x)dx$. The values of $R[K_{(r)}]$ for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are given in Table (2.2). Note that, the rate of converge for the variance of $\hat{f}^*(x)$ remains $O(nh^*)^{-1}$, the same as that of Estimator (1.1)

2.2.3 The Mean Square Error and the Smoothing Parameter of $\hat{f}^*(x)$

The MSE combines the variance and the squared bias of $\hat{f}^*(x)$ at a fixed point x to measure the quality of $\hat{f}^*(x)$, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x)) &= E(\hat{f}^*(x) - f(x))^2 \\
 &= \text{Var}(\hat{f}^*(x)) + (E\hat{f}^*(x) - f(x))^2 \\
 &\cong \frac{1}{nh^*} f(x)R[K_{(r)}] + [(-1)^r \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!} \right\} h^{*r} f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \\
 &= \frac{1}{nh^*} f(x)R[K_{(r)}] + \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!} \right\}^2 h^{*2r} [f^{(r)}(x)]^2. \tag{2.6}
 \end{aligned}$$

The value of h^* is obtained by considering the MSE as a function of h^* (say $D(h^*)$), differentiate $D(h^*)$ with respect to h^* and equating to zero, then solve the resulting equation with respect to h^* as the following:

r	$K_{(r)}$	$\mu_r(K_{(r)})$	Q_r	$R[K_{(r)}]$	V_r	T_r
2	$K_{(2)}$	1	0.5	0.2821	0.7764	0.4542
4	$K_{(4)}$	-3	-0.125	0.4760	1.1602	0.4616
6	$K_{(6)}$	15	0.020833	0.6240	1.4451	0.4678
8	$K_{(8)}$	-105	-0.00260417	0.7479	1.6818	0.4725
10	$K_{(10)}$	945	0.000260417	0.8565	1.8889	0.4761

Table (2.2): The values of $\mu_r(K_{(r)})$, Q_r , $R[K_{(r)}]$, V_r and T_r for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$.

Note that

$$\mu_r(K_{(r)}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} z^r K_{(r)}(z) dz, \quad Q_r = (-1)^r \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!} \right\}, \quad R[K_{(r)}] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K_{(r)}^2(z) dz,$$

$$V_r = \left[\frac{(r!)^2 R(K_{(r)})}{(2r) \mu_r^2(K_{(r)})} \right]^{1/(2r+1)}, \quad T_r = \frac{2r+1}{\{2r\}^{2r/(2r+1)} \{r!\}^{2/(2r+1)}} [R(K_{(r)})]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [\mu_r^2(K_{(r)})]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$$

and $K_{(r)}$, $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are given in Table (2.1).

$$\frac{-1}{nh^{*2}}f(x)R[K_{(r)}] + 2rh^{*2r-1}\left\{\frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!}\right\}^2 [f^{(r)}(x)]^2 = 0.$$

The solution of the above equation gives,

$$\frac{1}{nh^{*2}}f(x)R[K_{(r)}] = 2rh^{*2r-1}\left\{\frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!}\right\}^2 [f^{(r)}(x)]^2.$$

Multiple both sides by h^{*2} , then we obtain,

$$h^{*2r+1} = \frac{(r!)^2 f(x)R(K_{(r)})}{n(2r)[f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \mu_r^2(K_{(r)})}.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} h^* &= \left[\frac{(r!)^2 f(x)R(K_{(r)})}{n(2r)[f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \mu_r^2(K_{(r)})} \right]^{1/(2r+1)} \\ &= V_r \left[\frac{f(x)}{n[f^{(r)}(x)]^2} \right]^{1/(2r+1)}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where $V_r = \left[\frac{(r!)^2 R(K_{(r)})}{(2r)\mu_r^2(K_{(r)})} \right]^{1/(2r+1)}$. The values of V_r for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are given

in Table (2.2). Substituting the expression of h^* back into Formula (2.6) leads to

the smallest possible value of MSE for $\hat{f}^*(x)$, which is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
MSE \hat{f}^*(x) &= \frac{f(x)R[K_{(r)}]}{n \left[\frac{(r!)^2 f(x)R(K_{(r)})}{n(2r)[f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \mu_r^2(K_{(r)})} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}} + \\
&\quad \left\{ \frac{\mu_r(K_{(r)})}{r!} \right\}^2 \left\{ \left[\frac{(r!)^2 f(x)R(K_{(r)})}{n(2r)[f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \mu_r^2(K_{(r)})} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} \right\}^{2r} [f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \\
&= \left[\frac{2r+1}{\{2r\}^{2r/(2r+1)} \{r!\}^{2/(2r+1)}} \right] [f(x)R(K_{(r)})]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [f^{(r)}(x)]^2 \mu_r^2(K_{(r)})^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{-2r}{2r+1}} \\
&= T_r [f(x)]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [f^{(r)}(x)]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{-2r}{2r+1}}, \tag{2.8}
\end{aligned}$$

where $T_r = \frac{2r+1}{\{2r\}^{2r/(2r+1)} \{r!\}^{2/(2r+1)}} [R(K_{(r)})]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [\mu_r^2(K_{(r)})]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$. The values of T_r for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are given in Table (2.2). Note that the functions $K_{(r)}$, $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are given in Table (2.1).

We note here that, if the asymptotic mean integrated squared error (*MISE*) is to be used instead of the asymptotic *MSE* then the right hand side of equations (2.4), (2.5), (2.7) and (2.8) are slightly different and they become

$$Q_r h^{*r} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f^{(r)}(x) + o(h^{*r}), \frac{1}{nh^*} R[K_{(r)}] + o(n^{-1}), V_r \left[\frac{1}{n \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f^{(r)}(x)]^2 dx} \right]^{1/(2r+1)} \text{ and}$$

$$T_r \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f^{(r)}(x)]^2 dx \right\}^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{-2r}{2r+1}} \text{ respectively. For purpose of comparison, the}$$

using of *MISE* or *MSE* are equivalent.

2.3 The Proposed Estimator

Let X_1, \dots, X_n be a random sample of size n from a probability density function $f(x)$ that assumes to have r^{th} continuous derivatives. We propose to estimate $f(x)$ by using the following kernel estimator

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K\left(\frac{x - X_i}{jb}\right), \quad -\infty < x < \infty. \quad (2.9)$$

which we call it “additive kernel estimator”, where $\sum_{j=1}^d ja_j = 1$, K is the second-order kernel function satisfies condition (1.2), b is the smoothing parameter, d and a_j , $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ are constants introduced to control the magnitude of bias and variance of estimator $\tilde{f}(x)$.

The special case of Estimator (2.9) was studied by Eidous (2011). He derived the asymptotic bias and variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$ when $x=0$ and for the non-negative values of the random sample applying for line transect data. The asymptotic properties of $\tilde{f}(x)$ are derived in the following subsections.

2.3.1 The Expected Value and the Bias of $\tilde{f}(x)$

The expected value of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is:

$$E(\tilde{f}(x)) = E\left[(nb)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K\{(x - X_i)/jb\}\right]$$

$$= (nb)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^d a_j n E K \{(x - X_i)/jb\}.$$

Now, the expected value of $K \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\}$ is

$$E \left(K \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} \right) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} f(x) dx .$$

Let $u = \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\}$ and use the Taylor's series expansion of $f(x - jbu)$ around x ,

then,

$$\begin{aligned} E \left(K \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} \right) &= jb \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(u) f(x - jbu) du \\ &= jb \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(u) \left[f(x) - jbu f'(x) + \frac{j^2 b^2 u^2 f''(x)}{2!} + \frac{j^3 b^3 u^3 f'''(x)}{3!} + \dots \right] du \\ &= jbf(x) - j^2 b^2 f'(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u K(u) du + \frac{j^3 b^3 f''(x)}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 K(u) du + \dots \\ &= jbf(x) - j^2 b^2 f'(x) \mu_1(K) + \frac{j^3 b^3 f''(x)}{2} \mu_2(K) + \dots , \end{aligned}$$

where $\mu_i(K) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^i K(u) du$. Now, suppose that the smoothing parameter and the sample size are related such that $b \rightarrow 0$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, then the expected value of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\tilde{f}(x)) &= E \left((nb)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K \{(x - X_i)/jb\} \right) \\ &= (b)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^d a_j E(K \{(x - X_i)/jb\}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{j=1}^d a_j [jf(x) - j^2bf'(x)\mu_1(K) + \frac{j^3b^2f''(x)\mu_2(K)}{2} + \dots] \\
&= f(x)\sum_{j=1}^d ja_j - bf'(x)\mu_1(K)\sum_{j=1}^d j^2a_j + \frac{b^2f''(x)}{2}\mu_2(K)\sum_{j=1}^d j^3a_j \\
&\quad + \dots + \frac{b^rf^{(r)}(x)}{r!}\mu_r(K)\sum_{j=1}^d j^{r+1}a_j + o(b^r). \\
&= f(x)A_1 - bf^{(1)}(x)\mu_1(K)A_2 + \frac{b^2}{2}f^{(2)}(x)\mu_2(K)A_3 \\
&\quad + \dots + \frac{b^rf^{(r)}(x)}{r!}\mu_r(K)A_{r+1} + o(b^r), \quad (2.10)
\end{aligned}$$

where $A_l = \sum_{j=1}^d j^l a_j$ and $f^{(r)}(x)$ is the r^{th} derivative of $f(x)$. Therefore, under the constraints $A_1 = 1$ and $A_3 = A_5 = A_7 = \dots = A_{r-1} = 0$, the bias of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Bias } \tilde{f}(x) &= E\tilde{f}(x) - f(x). \\
&= \frac{b^rf^{(r)}(x)\mu_r(K)A_{r+1}}{r!} + o(b^r) \\
&= QQ_r b^r f^{(r)}(x) + o(b^r), \quad (2.11)
\end{aligned}$$

where $QQ_r = \frac{\mu_r(K)A_{r+1}}{r!}$. Because the second order kernel K is assumed to be even function, then $\mu_r(K) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^r K(u)du = 0$, for odd values of r . That is $\mu_1(K) = \mu_3(K) = \mu_5(K) = \dots = 0$. Therefore, the terms $bf^{(1)}(x)\mu_1(K)A_2$, $\frac{b^3f^{(3)}(x)}{3!}\mu_3(K)A_4$, $\frac{b^5f^{(5)}(x)}{5!}\mu_5(K)A_6$, ... are vanished without assuming $A_2 = A_4 =$

$A_6 = \dots = 0$. In other words and since r is even value, the constraints $A_1 = 1$ and $A_3 = A_5 = A_7 = \dots = A_{r-1} = 0$ should be valid to obtain $O(b^r)$ bias for $\tilde{f}(x)$.

2.3.2 The Variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$

In this subsection, we will derive the asymptotic variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$ under the assumption $nb \rightarrow \infty$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$. The variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} Var(\tilde{f}(x)) &= Var((nb)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K\{(x - X_i)/jb\}) \\ &= \frac{1}{nb^2} Var[\sum_{j=1}^d a_j (K\{(x - X_i)/jb\})] \\ &= \frac{1}{nb^2} \left[E(\sum_{j=1}^d a_j K\{(x - X_i)/jb\})^2 - (\sum_{j=1}^d a_j EK\{(x - X_i)/jb\})^2 \right]. \end{aligned}$$

By substituting the expression of $EK[(x - X_i)/jb]$ in the second term of the last expression then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} Var(\tilde{f}(x)) &= \frac{1}{nb^2} E[\sum_{j=1}^d a_j (K\{(x - X_i)/jb\})]^2 + o(n^{-1}) \\ &= \frac{1}{nb^2} E(\sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{l=1}^d a_j a_l K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right] K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{lb} \right]) + o(n^{-1}) \\ &= \frac{1}{nb^2} E(\sum_{j=1}^d a_j^2 K^2 \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} + 2 \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right] K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{lb} \right]) + o(n^{-1}) \\ &= \frac{1}{nb^2} (\sum_{j=1}^d a_j^2 EK^2 \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} + 2 \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l E(K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right] K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{lb} \right])) + o(n^{-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
EK^2 \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2 \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} f(x) dx \\
&= jb \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) f(x - jhu) du \\
&= jb \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) [f(x) - jbu f'(x) + \frac{j^2 b^2 u^2 f''(x)}{2} + \dots] du \\
&= jbf(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du - j^2 b^2 f'(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u K^2(u) du + \dots,
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{nb^2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^d a_j^2 EK^2 \left\{ \frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right\} \right) &= \\
&= \frac{1}{nb^2} \sum_{j=1}^d a_j^2 [jbf(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du - j^2 b^2 f'(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u K^2(u) du + \dots] \\
&= \frac{1}{nb} f(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d ja_j^2 - \frac{1}{n} f'(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d j^2 a_j^2 + o\left(\frac{h}{n}\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{nb} f(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d ja_j^2 + o(n^{-1}).
\end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
EK \left[\frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right] K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{lb} \right] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right] K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{lb} \right] f(x) dx \\
&= b \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] f(x - bu) du
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= b \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] \left[f(x) - buf'(x) + \frac{b^2 u^2 f''(x)}{2} + \dots \right] du \\
&= bf(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du - b^2 f'(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du + \dots \\
&= bf(x)D_1 - b^2 f'(x)D_2 + \dots,
\end{aligned}$$

where $D_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du$ and $D_2 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{2}{nb^2} \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l EK \left[\frac{x-X_i}{jb} \right] K \left[\frac{x-X_i}{lb} \right] \\
&= \frac{2}{nb^2} \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l [bf(x)D_1 - b^2 f'(x)D_2 + \dots] \\
&= \frac{2f(x)}{nb} \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l D_1 - \frac{2}{n} f'(x) \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l D_2 + o\left(\frac{b}{n}\right) \\
&= \frac{2f(x)}{nb} \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du + o(n^{-1}).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the asymptotic variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is

$$Var(\tilde{f}(x)) =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{f(x)}{nb} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j^2 + \frac{2f(x)}{nb} \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du + o(n^{-1}) \\
&= \frac{f(x)}{nb} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j^2 + 2 \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du \right\} + o(n^{-1}) \\
&= \frac{f(x)}{nb} S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) + o(n^{-1}), \tag{2.12}
\end{aligned}$$

where $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j^2 + 2 \sum_{j<l} \sum a_j a_l \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du$. Note that the convergence rate for variance of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is $O(nb)^{-1}$, the same as that of the classical kernel estimator and that of higher-order kernel estimator.

2.3.3 The Mean Square Error and the Smoothing Parameter of $\tilde{f}(x)$

The asymptotic mean square error (MSE) of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{MSE}(\tilde{f}(x)) &= E(\tilde{f}(x) - f(x))^2 \\
&= \text{Var}(\tilde{f}(x)) + (\text{Bias } \tilde{f}(x))^2 \\
&= \frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{nb} + \left(\frac{b^r f^{(r)}(x) \mu_r(K) A_{r+1}}{r!} \right)^2 \\
&= \frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{nb} + \frac{b^{2r} f^{(r)2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2}{(r!)^2}. \tag{2.13}
\end{aligned}$$

The value of b can be obtained by considering the MSE of $\tilde{f}(x)$ as a function of b (say $T(b)$), differentiate $T(b)$ with respect to b and equating to zero, then solve the resulting equation with respect to b to obtain,

$$\frac{-f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{nb^2} + \frac{2rb^{2r-1} f^{(r)2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2}{(r!)^2} = 0$$

which implies

$$\frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{nb^2} = \frac{2rb^{2r-1} f^{(r)2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2}{(r!)^2}$$

Multiple both sides by b^2 , then we obtain,

$$\frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{n} = \frac{2rb^{2r+1} f^{(r)^2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2}{(r!)^2},$$

and then,

$$\begin{aligned} b &= \left[\frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) (r!)^2}{n(2r) f^{(r)^2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}. \\ &= VV_r \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(r)^2}(x)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{-1}{2r+1}}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

where $VV_r = \left[\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) (r!)^2}{(2r) f^{(r)^2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$. Note that, the smoothing parameter $b \rightarrow 0$

when $n \rightarrow \infty$. Also, the term $VV_r \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(r)^2}(x)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ but at a

rate slower than n because $\frac{2r}{2r+1} < 1$. Now, by substituting the above expression of

b back into Formula (2.13) leads to the smallest possible MSE of $\tilde{f}(x)$.

$MSE(\tilde{f}(x)) =$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{\left[\frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) (r!)^2}{n(2r) f^{(r)^2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}} + \frac{\left(\left[\frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) (r!)^2}{n(2r) f^{(r)^2}(x) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} \right)^{2c} [f^{(r)^2}(x)] [\mu_r^2(K)] [A_{r+1}^2]}{(r!)^2}. \\ &= \left[\frac{2r+1}{\{2r\}^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} \{r!\}^{\frac{2}{2r+1}}} \right] [f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [f^{(r)^2}(x) \mu_r^2(k) A_{r+1}^2]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{-2r}{2r+1}} \\ &= TT_r [f(x)]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [f^{(r)^2}(x)]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} [n]^{\frac{-2r}{2r+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

where $TT_r = \frac{2r+1}{\{2r\}^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} \{r!\}^{\frac{2}{2r+1}}} [S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [\mu_r^2(k) A_{r+1}^2]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$. Equation

(2.15) implies that, if the pdf $f(x)$ has r continuous derivatives and by picking

suitable values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d such that $A_1 = 1$ and $A_3 = A_5 = A_7 = \dots = A_{r-1} = 0$, the speed of convergence can be improved over that $O(n)^{-4/5}$ found for $r = 2$ (the convergence rate of MSE for the classical kernel estimator). For example, when $r = 4$, the MSE converges at rate $O(n)^{-8/9}$, which is better than that $O(n)^{-4/5}$. An inspection of the asymptotic MSE of the higher-order kernel estimator (Equation 2.8) leads us to the same conclusion, provided that the higher-order kernel function $K_{(r)}$ that satisfies (2.1) is obtained. The relationship between the smoothing parameters, asymptotic biases, asymptotic variances and asymptotic mean square errors of the higher-order kernel estimator, $\hat{f}^*(x)$ and the proposed estimator, $\tilde{f}(x)$ are given in Section (2.4). Despite that the two estimators $\hat{f}^*(x)$ and $\tilde{f}(x)$ can achieve $O(n)^{\frac{-2r}{2r+1}}$, $r = 2, 4, 6, \dots$, a preference for $\tilde{f}(x)$ over $\hat{f}^*(x)$ can be obtained as a comparison study in Chapter (3) demonstrated.

2.4. Relationship Between the Asymptotic Properties of $\tilde{f}(x)$ and $\hat{f}^*(x)$

The optimal formula of the smoothing parameter b for the proposed estimator is

$$b = VV_r \left(\frac{f(x)}{f^r(x)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} + n^{-1/2r+1}.$$

Where $VV_r = \left(\frac{(r!)^2 S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{2r \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$. Therefore b and h^* are related by the following relationship

$$b \cong \frac{VV_r}{V_r} h^*$$

$$b \cong \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) \mu_r^2(K_r)}{\mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2 R(K_r)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} h^*. \quad (2.16)$$

Note that ,if $r = 2$ then $\mu_r^2(K) = \mu_r^2(K_r)$.

Suppose that b and h^* are related according to formula (2.16), then the asymptotic

bias ,variance and MSE of $\tilde{f}(x)$ and $\hat{f}^*(x)$ are related as the following :

I. Let $QQ_r = \frac{\mu_r(K) A_{r+1}}{r!}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Bias}(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong QQ_r b^r f^{(r)}(x) \\ &\cong QQ_r \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) \mu_r^2(K_r)}{\mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2 R(K_r)} \right)^{\frac{r}{2r+1}} h^{*r} f^{(r)}(x) \\ &\cong \frac{QQ_r}{Q_r} \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) \mu_r^2(K_r)}{\mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2 R(K_r)} \right)^{\frac{r}{2r+1}} \text{Bias}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\ &\cong \frac{\mu_r(K) A_{r+1}}{(-1)^r \mu_r(K_r)} \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) \mu_r^2(K_r)}{\mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2 R(K_r)} \right)^{\frac{r}{2r+1}} \text{Bias}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

II. $\text{Var}(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong \frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{nb}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{f(x) S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{nh^*} \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) \mu_r^2(K_r)}{\mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2 R(K_r)} \right)^{\frac{-1}{2r+1}} \\ &= [S^{2r}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) A_{r+1}^2]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} \left[\frac{\mu_r^2(K)}{\mu_r^2(K_r) R^{2r}(K_r)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} \text{Var}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

III. Let $TT_r = (2r + 1)[(2r)^{2r} (r!)^2]^{\frac{-1}{2r+1}} [S^{2r}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) A_{r+1}^2 \mu_r^2(K)]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$

Then the asymptotic mean square error of $\tilde{f}(x)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
MSE(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong TT_r \left(f^{(r)^2}(x) f^{2r}(x) n^{-2r} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} \\
&\cong \frac{TT_r}{T_r} MSE(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\
&\cong \left(\frac{S^{2r}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) A_{r+1}^2 \mu_r^2(K)}{\mu_r^2(K_r) R^{2r}(K_r)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2r+1}} MSE(\hat{f}^*(x)) \quad (2.19)
\end{aligned}$$

To simplify formulas (2.16), (2.17), (2.18) and (2.19), let us consider the five values of $r = 2, 4, 6, 8$ and 10 and take the second order kernel to be $N(0,1)$ (i.e. $K = K_2 = N(0,1)$). Then $\mu_2(K) = 1$, $\mu_4(K) = 3$, $\mu_6(K) = 15$, $\mu_8(K) = 105$ and $\mu_{10}(K) = 945$. Also $\mu_r(K_r)$ and $R(K_r)$ for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8$ and 10 are given in table (2.2).

1- if $r = 2$ then

$$b \cong 1.2880 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_3^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{5}} h^*,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Bias(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong 1.6590 A_3 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_3^2} \right)^{\frac{2}{5}} Bias(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\
&\cong 1.6590 A_3^{\frac{1}{5}} (S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{2}{5}} Bias(\hat{f}^*(x))
\end{aligned}$$

$$Var(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 2.7522 A_3^{\frac{2}{5}} (S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{4}{5}} Var(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

and

$$MSE(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 2.7522 (S^4(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) A_3^2)^{\frac{1}{5}} MSE(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

2- if $r = 4$ then

$$b \cong 1.0860 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_5^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{9}} h^*.$$

$$\begin{aligned} Bias(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong -1.3909 A_5 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_5^2} \right)^{\frac{4}{9}} Bias(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\ &\cong -1.3909 (A_5 S^4(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{9}} Bias(\hat{f}^*(x)) \end{aligned}$$

$$Var(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.9345 (A_5^2 S^8(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{9}} Var(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

and

$$MSE(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.9345 (A_5^2 S^8(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{9}} MSE(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

3- if $r = 6$ then

$$b \cong 1.03694 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_7^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{13}} h^*.$$

$$\begin{aligned} Bias(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong 1.2432 A_7 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_7^2} \right)^{\frac{6}{13}} Bias(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\ &\cong -1.2432 (A_7 S^6(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{13}} Bias(\hat{f}^*(x)) \end{aligned}$$

$$Var(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.5455 (A_7^2 S^{12}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{13}} Var(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

and

$$MSE(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.5455 (A_7^2 S^{12}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{13}} MSE(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

4- if $r = 8$ then

$$b \cong 1.0172 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_9^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{17}} h^*.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Bias}(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong -1.1465 A_9 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_9^2} \right)^{\frac{8}{17}} \text{Bias}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\ &\cong -1.1465 (A_9 S^8(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{17}} \text{Bias}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Var}(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.3144 (A_9^2 S^{16}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{17}} \text{Var}(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

and

$$\text{MSE}(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.3144 (A_9^2 S^{16}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{17}} \text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

5- if $r = 10$ then

$$b \cong 1.0074 \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_{11}^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{21}} h^*.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Bias}(\tilde{f}(x)) &\cong 1.0766 A_{11} \left(\frac{S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{A_{11}^2} \right)^{\frac{10}{21}} \text{Bias}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \\ &\cong -1.0766 (A_{11} S^{10}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{21}} \text{Bias}(\hat{f}^*(x)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Var}(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.1590 (A_{11}^2 S^{20}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{21}} \text{Var}(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

and

$$\text{MSE}(\tilde{f}(x)) \cong 1.590 (A_{11}^2 S^{20}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d))^{\frac{1}{21}} \text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))$$

CHAPTER THREE

ASYMPTOTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN HIGHER ORDER KERNEL AND PROPOSED ESTIMATOR

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, asymptotic comparison between the proposed estimator, $\tilde{f}(x)$ and the higher-order kernel estimator, $\hat{f}^*(x)$ is performed. This required to determine the proposed estimator weights a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d and the integer constant d . The global measure; asymptotic mean square error (MSE) is considered for purpose of comparison, which is equivalent to use the asymptotic mean integrated squares error ($MISE$).

3.2 Construction of the Proposed Estimator

Recall that the expected value of the proposed estimator is (Formula 2.10)

$$f(x)A_1 - bf^{(1)}(x)\mu_1(K)A_2 + \frac{b^2}{2}f^{(2)}(x)\mu_2(K)A_3 \\ + \dots + \frac{b^r f^{(r)}(x)}{r!} \mu_r(K)A_{r+1} + o(b^r),$$

where $A_l = \sum_{j=1}^d j^l a_j$, $r = 2, 4, 6, \dots$ and

$$\mu_r(K) = \begin{cases} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} z^r K(z) dz & r = 2, 4, 6, \dots \\ 0 & r = 1, 3, 5, \dots \end{cases}.$$

To obtain $O(b^r)$ bias for $\tilde{f}(x)$, the constraints $A_1 = 1$ and $A_3 = A_5 = A_7 = \dots = A_{r-1} = 0$ should be satisfied. For example, to obtain $O(b^2)$, only $A_1 = 1$ is required, while to obtain $O(b^4)$ the constraints $A_1 = 1$ and $A_3 = 0$ are required and so on. In addition to the above constraints and for each even value of r , the term A_{r+1} should not equal zero (i.e. $A_{r+1} \neq 0$). If $A_{r+1} = 0$ then we obtain $O(b^{r+2})$ bias not $O(b^r)$. This also can be concluded by inspection the formula of the smoothing parameter b (Formula 2.14), which is no longer applicable if $A_{r+1} = 0$. Therefore and in addition to the above constraints we need to introduce another constraint about the value of A_{r+1} . In this study, we chose to fix the value of A_{r+1} at a specific value λ chosen to be 0.5 for all different values of r .

To construct the proposed estimator, the weights a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d and the constant d should be determined. If a $O(b^r)$ bias is required, then we need to find a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d under the constraints $A_1 = 1$, $A_3 = A_5 = A_7 = \dots = A_{r-1} = 0$ and $A_{r+1} = \lambda$. Because r is even value then the number of constraints is $\frac{r}{2} + 1$. This requires the integer value of d to be $\frac{r}{2} + 1$ (i.e. $d = \frac{r}{2} + 1$). For example, if $r = 2$ then the required constraints on a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are $A_1 = a_1 + 2a_2 + \dots + da_d = 1$ and $A_3 = a_1 + 8a_2 + \dots + d^3a_d = \lambda$. The unique solution for the two equations

can be obtained if $d = \frac{r}{2} + 1$ (i.e. $d = 2$). The convergence rate for a bias of $\tilde{f}(x)$ and the corresponding required constraints are given in Table (3.1).

Now, the other more logical method to determine a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d is to find their values that minimize the asymptotic MSE of $\tilde{f}(x)$ under the above mentioned constraints. The word minimization technique requires d to be greater than $\frac{r}{2} + 1$ (i.e. $d > \frac{r}{2} + 1$). We note here that, when d equals the number of constraints then the values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are determined without minimization the MSE , while the increasing in the value of d over the number of constraints gives many sets of candidate values for the weights and we need to determine the set of values that minimize MSE .

In the following sections, we will consider a $O(b^r)$ bias for both estimators; $\hat{f}^*(x)$ and $\tilde{f}(x)$, where the five even values $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$ are studied separately. For each value of r , the asymptotic properties of the proposed estimator $\tilde{f}(x)$ are investigated by choosing the three values of d ; $d = \frac{r}{2} + 1$ (no minimization for MSE), $d = \frac{r}{2} + 2$ and $d = \frac{r}{2} + 3$. The value of λ is taken to be 0.5 for all different cases and the second order kernel function $K_{(2)} = K$ is $N(0, 1)$.

3.3 The Case $O(b^2)$ Bias

As we mentioned above, given that $O(b^r)$ bias is desirable, there are several ways to construct the proposed estimator, $\tilde{f}(x)$, i.e. to determine d and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d . If the order of bias is $O(b^2)$ (i.e. $r = 2$) then we will consider three values of d ; $d = 2, 3, 4$ according to the above rules. Therefore, we can obtain three proposed estimators, which are

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K\left(\frac{x - X_i}{jb}\right), \quad d = 2, 3, 4.$$

The values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are determined under the two constraints:

$$A_1 = \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j = 1 \text{ and } A_3 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^3 a_j = (\lambda = 0.5). \quad (3.1)$$

The three cases of d are treated as the following:

- (1) If $d = 2$, then the solution of the two equations in (3.1) gives

$$a_1 = 1.1667 \text{ and } a_2 = -0.0833.$$

In addition,

$$QQ_2 = 0.25, S(a_1, a_2) = 0.3185, VV_2 = 1.0496 \text{ and } TT_2 = 0.3793.$$

- (2) If $d = 3$, then the minimization of $S(a_1, a_2, a_3)$ subject to the constraints of

(3.1) gives

$$a_1 = -0.6355, \quad a_2 = 1.358 \text{ and } a_3 = -0.3604,$$

which yields,

$$QQ_2 = 0.25, S(a_1, a_2, a_3) = 0.1722, VV_2 = 0.9281 \text{ and } TT_2 = 0.2319.$$

(3) If $d = 4$, then the minimization of $S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ subject to the constraints of (3.1) gives

$$a_1 = 0.3898, a_2 = -1.5648, a_3 = 2.2480 \text{ and } a_4 = -0.7510,$$

and then,

$$QQ_2 = 0.25, S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) = 0.1126, VV_2 = 0.8526 \text{ and } TT_2 = 0.1651$$

The above three values of d corresponds three different estimators based on $\tilde{f}(x)$.

Now, let $b_r^{(d)}$ and $MSE_r^{(d)}$ be the smoothing parameter and the asymptotic mean square error of $\tilde{f}(x)$, then based on the above values of r , d and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d , we obtain,

$$b_2^{(2)} = 1.0496 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(2)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/5} [n]^{-1/5}, \quad MSE_2^{(2)} = 0.3793 [f(x)]^{4/5} [f^{(2)^2}(x)]^{1/5} [n]^{-4/5}$$

$$b_2^{(3)} = 0.9281 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(2)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/5} [n]^{-1/5}, \quad MSE_2^{(3)} = 0.2319 [f(x)]^{4/5} [f^{(2)^2}(x)]^{1/5} [n]^{-4/5}$$

and

$$b_2^{(4)} = 0.8526 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(2)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/5} [n]^{-1/5}, \quad MSE_2^{(4)} = 0.1651 [f(x)]^{4/5} [f^{(2)^2}(x)]^{1/5} [n]^{-4/5}.$$

For $r = 2$ and based on Table (2.2), the smoothing parameter h^* and the MSE of the higher-order kernel estimator $\hat{f}^*(x)$ are respectively

$$h^* = 0.7764 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(2)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/5} [n]^{-1/5}, \quad MSE = 0.4542 [f(x)]^{4/5} [f^{(2)^2}(x)]^{1/5} [n]^{-4/5}.$$

3.4 The Case $O(b^4)$ Bias

The case $O(b^4)$ bias for $\tilde{f}(x)$ indicates $r = 4$ and therefore the suggested three values of d are $d = 3, 4, 5$. The corresponding proposed estimator is

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K\left(\frac{x - X_i}{jb}\right), \quad d = 3, 4, 5.$$

The values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are determined under the three constraints:

$$A_1 = \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j = 1, A_3 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^3 a_j = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad A_5 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^5 a_j = (\lambda = 0.5) \quad (3.2)$$

(1) If $d = 3$, we need to solve the three equations of (3.2) simultaneously. This gives

$$a_1 = 1.5208, \quad a_2 = -0.3167 \quad \text{and} \quad a_3 = 0.0375,$$

Based on these values of a_1, a_2, a_3 , we obtain,

$$QQ_4 = 0.0625, S(a_1, a_2, a_3) = 0.3939, VV_4 = 1.3252 \quad \text{and} \quad TT_4 = 0.3344.$$

Also,

$$b_4^{(3)} = 1.3252 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(4)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/9} [n]^{-1/9} \quad \text{and} \quad MSE_4^{(3)} = 0.3344 [f(x)]^{8/9} [f^{(4)^2}(x)]^{1/9} [n]^{-8/9}$$

(2) If $d = 4$, then we want to minimize $S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ subject to the three constraints of (3.2), which gives

$$a_1 = -0.7091, \quad a_2 = 1.9132, \quad a_3 = -0.9182 \quad \text{and} \quad a_4 = 0.1593.$$

These values and the values $r = 4$ and $d = 4$ give,

$$QQ_4 = 0.0625, \quad S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) = 0.2088, \quad VV_4 = 1.2350 \quad \text{and} \quad TT_4 = 0.1902.$$

Also,

$$b_4^{(4)} = 1.235 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(4)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/9} [n]^{-1/9} \quad \text{and} \quad MSE_4^{(4)} = 0.1902 [f(x)]^{8/9} [f^{(4)^2}(x)]^{1/9} [n]^{-8/9}$$

(3) If $d = 5$, then

$$a_1 = 0.4176, \quad a_2 = -1.9654, \quad a_3 = 3.6927, \quad a_4 = -2.2146 \quad \text{and} \quad a_5 = -2.2146,$$

which are obtained by minimizing $S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5)$ subject to the constraints of (3.2). Accordingly, we obtain,

$$QQ_4 = 0.0625, \quad S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5) = 0.1403, \quad VV_4 = 1.1816 \quad \text{and} \quad TT_4 = 0.1336.$$

Also,

$$b_4^{(5)} = 1.1816 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(4)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/9} [n]^{-1/9} \quad \text{and} \quad MSE_4^{(5)} = 0.1336 [f(x)]^{8/9} [f^{(4)^2}(x)]^{1/9} [n]^{-8/9}.$$

If $r = 4$, we can use Table (2.2) to produce the smoothing parameter and the asymptotic (MSE) of the higher-order kernel which are respectively given by

$$h^* = 1.1602 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(4)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/9} [n]^{-1/9} \quad \text{and} \quad MSE = 0.4616 [f(x)]^{8/9} [f^{(4)^2}(x)]^{1/9} [n]^{-8/9}$$

3.5 The Case $O(h^6)$ Bias

The case $O(b^6)$ bias for $\tilde{f}(x)$ indicates $r = 6$ and therefore the suggested three values of d are $d = 4, 5, 6$. The corresponding proposed estimator is

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K \left(\frac{x - X_i}{jb} \right), \quad d = 4, 5, 6.$$

The values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are determined under the four constraints:

$$A_1 = \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j = 1, A_3 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^3 a_j = 0, A_5 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^5 a_j = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$A_7 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^7 a_j = (\lambda = 0.5) \tag{3.3}$$

(1) If $d = 4$, we need to solve the four equations of (3.3) simultaneously. This gives

$$a_1 = 1.5986, a_2 = -1.9654, a_3 = 0.0756 \text{ and } a_4 = -0.0070$$

Based on these values of a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 , we obtain,

$$QQ_6 = 0.0104, S(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) = 0.4064, VV_6 = 1.5556 \text{ and } TT_6 = 0.2831.$$

Also,

$$b_6^{(4)} = 1.5556 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(6)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/13} [n]^{-1/13} \text{ and } MSE_6^{(4)} = 0.2831 [f(x)]^{12/13} [f^{(6)^2}(x)]^{1/13} [n]^{-12/13}$$

(2) If $d = 5$, then we want to minimize $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_5)$ subject to the four constraints of (3.3), which gives

$$a_1 = -0.7298, a_2 = 2.2624, a_3 = -1.4212, a_4 = 0.4365 \text{ and}$$

$$a_5 = -0.0554$$

These values and the values $r = 6$ and $d = 5$ give,

$$QQ_6 = 0.0104, S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_5) = 0.2265, VV_6 = 1.4871 \text{ and } TT_6 = 0.1650$$

Also,

$$b_6^{(5)} = 1.4871 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(4)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/13} [n]^{-1/13} \text{ and } MSE_6^{(5)} = 0.1650 [f(x)]^{12/13} [f^{(6)^2}(x)]^{1/13} [n]^{-12/13}$$

(3) If $d = 6$, then

$$a_1 = 0.4258, a_2 = -2.2227, a_3 = 4.9473, a_4 = -4.0029 \text{ and } a_5 = 1.5064,$$

$$a_6 = -0.2238$$

which are obtained by minimizing $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6)$ subject to the constraints of (3.3). Accordingly, we obtain,

$$QQ_6 = 0.0104, S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6) = 0.1570, VV_6 = 1.4458 \text{ and } TT_6 = 0.1177.$$

Also,

$$b_6^{(6)} = 1.4458 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(6)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/13} [n]^{-1/13} \text{ and } MSE_6^{(6)} = 0.1177 [f(x)]^{12/13} [f^{(6)^2}(x)]^{1/13} [n]^{-12/13}.$$

If $r = 6$, we can use Table (2.2) to produce the smoothing parameter and the asymptotic (MSE) of the higher-order kernel which are respectively given by

$$h^* = 1.4451 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(6)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/13} [n]^{-1/13} \text{ and } MSE = 0.4678 [f(x)]^{12/13} [f^{(6)^2}(x)]^{1/13} [n]^{-12/13}$$

3.6 The Case $O(h^8)$ Bias

The case $O(b^8)$ bias for $\tilde{f}(x)$ indicates $r = 8$ and therefore the suggested three values of d are $d = 5, 6, 7$. The corresponding proposed estimator is

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K \left(\frac{x - X_i}{jb} \right), \quad d = 5, 6, 7.$$

The values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are determined under the five constraints:

$$A_1 = \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j = 1, A_3 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^3 a_j = 0, A_5 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^5 a_j = 0$$

$$A_7 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^7 a_j = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad A_9 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^9 a_j = (\lambda = 0.5) \quad (3.4)$$

(1) If $d = 5$, we need to solve the five equations of (3.4) simultaneously. This gives

$$a_1 = 1.6667, \quad a_2 = -0.4763, \quad a_3 = 0.1191, \quad a_4 = -0.0199$$

$$\text{and } a_5 = -0.0016$$

Based on these values of a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 , we obtain,

$$QQ_8 = 0.0013, \quad S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_5) = 0.4171, \quad VV_8 = 1.7631 \quad \text{and}$$

$$TT_8 = 0.2514.$$

Also,

$$b_8^{(5)} = 1.7631 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(8)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/17} [n]^{-1/17} \quad \text{and} \quad MSE_8^{(5)} = 0.2514 [f(x)]^{16/17} [f^{(8)^2}(x)]^{1/17} [n]^{-16/17}$$

(2) If $d = 6$, then we want to minimize $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6)$ subject to the five constraints of (3.4), which gives

$$a_1 = -0.7445, \quad a_2 = 2.5377, \quad a_3 = -1.8902, \quad a_4 = 0.7839,$$

$$a_5 = -0.1811 \quad \text{and} \quad a_6 = -0.0183$$

These values and the values $r = 8$ and $d = 6$ give,

$$QQ_8 = 0.0013, \quad S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6) = 0.2385, \quad VV_8 = 1.7061 \quad \text{and} \quad TT_8 = 0.1485$$

Also,

$$b_8^{(6)} = 1.7061 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(8)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/17} [n]^{-1/17} \text{ and } MSE_8^{(6)} = 0.1485 [f(x)]^{16/17} [f^{(8)^2}(x)]^{1/17} [n]^{-16/17}$$

(3) If $d = 7$, then

$$a_1 = 0.4290, a_2 = -2.4132, a_3 = 6.0559, a_4 = -5.9421, a_5 = 3.0752,$$

$$a_6 = -0.8434 \text{ and } a_7 = 0.0975$$

which are obtained by minimizing $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_7)$ subject to the constraints of (3.4). Accordingly, we obtain,

$$QQ_8 = 0.0013, S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_7) = 0.1680, VV_8 = 1.6776 \text{ and } TT_8 = 0.1073.$$

Also,

$$b_8^{(7)} = 1.6776 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(8)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/17} [n]^{-1/17} \text{ and } MSE_8^{(7)} = 0.1073 [f(x)]^{16/17} [f^{(8)^2}(x)]^{1/17} [n]^{-16/17}.$$

If $r = 8$, we can use Table (2.2) to produce the smoothing parameter and the asymptotic (MSE) of the higher-order kernel which are respectively given by

$$h^* = 1.6818 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(8)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/17} [n]^{-1/17} \text{ and } MSE = 0.4725 [f(x)]^{16/17} [f^{(8)^2}(x)]^{1/17} [n]^{-16/17}$$

3.7 The Case $O(h^{10})$ Bias

The case $O(b^{10})$ bias for $\tilde{f}(x)$ indicates $r = 10$ and therefore the suggested three values of d are $d = 6, 7, 8$. The corresponding proposed estimator is

$$\tilde{f}(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{j=1}^d \sum_{i=1}^n a_j K \left(\frac{x - X_i}{jb} \right), \quad d = 6, 7, 8.$$

The values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d are determined under the six constraints:

$$A_1 = \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j = 1 \quad , \quad A_3 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^3 a_j = 0 \quad , \quad A_5 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^5 a_j = 0 \quad , \quad A_7 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^7 a_j = 0, A_9 = \sum_{j=1}^d j^9 a_j = 0 \text{ and } A_{11} = \sum_{j=1}^d j^{11} a_j = (\lambda = 0.5) \quad (3.5)$$

(1) If $d = 6$, we need to solve the six equations of (3.5) simultaneously. This gives

$$a_1 = 1.7143 \quad , \quad a_2 = -0.5357 \quad , \quad a_3 = 0.1587 \quad , \quad a_4 = -0.0357$$

$$a_5 = 0.0052 \text{ and } a_6 = -0.0004$$

Based on these values of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6 , we obtain,

$$QQ_{10} = 0.00013, \quad S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6) = 0.4243, \quad VV_{10} = 1.9514 \text{ and}$$

$$TT_{10} = 0.2283.$$

Also,

$$b_{10}^{(6)} = 1.9514 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(10)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/21} [n]^{-1/21} \text{ and } MSE_{10}^{(6)} = 0.2282 [f(x)]^{20/21} [f^{(10)^2}(x)]^{1/21} [n]^{-20/21}$$

(2) If $d = 7$, then we want to minimize $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_7)$ subject to the six constraints of (3.5), which gives

$$a_1 = -0.7546 \quad , \quad a_2 = 2.7562 \quad , \quad a_3 = -2.3102 \quad , \quad a_4 = 1.1613 \quad ,$$

$$a_5 = -0.3689, a_6 = 0.0687 \text{ and } a_7 = -0.0058$$

These values and the values $r = 10$ and $d = 7$ give,

$$QQ_{10} = 0.00013, \quad S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_7) = 0.2471, \quad VV_{10} = 1.9018 \text{ and } TT_{10} = 0.1364$$

Also,

$$b_{10}^{(7)} = 1.9018 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(10)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/21} [n]^{-1/21} \text{ and } MSE_{10}^{(7)} = 0.1364 [f(x)]^{20/21} [f^{(10)^2}(x)]^{1/21} [n]^{-20/21}$$

(3) If $d = 8$, then

$$a_1 = 0.4149, a_2 = -2.5013, a_3 = 6.9279, a_4 = -7.8105, a_5 = 4.9805,$$

$$a_6 = -1.19036, a_7 = 0.4107 \text{ and } a_8 = -0.0388$$

which are obtained by minimizing $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_8)$ subject to the constraints of (3.5). Accordingly, we obtain,

$$QQ_{10} = 0.00013, S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_8) = 0.1775, VV_{10} = 1.8721 \text{ and } TT_{10} = 0.0996.$$

Also,

$$b_{10}^{(8)} = 1.8721 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(10)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/21} [n]^{-1/21} \text{ and } MSE_{10}^{(8)} = 0.0996 [f(x)]^{20/21} [f^{(10)^2}(x)]^{1/21} [n]^{-20/21}.$$

If $r = 10$, we can use Table (2.2) to produce the smoothing parameter and the asymptotic (MSE) of the higher-order kernel which are respectively given by

$$h^* = 1.8889 \left[\frac{f(x)}{f^{(10)^2}(x)} \right]^{1/21} [n]^{-1/21} \text{ and } MSE = 0.4761 [f(x)]^{20/21} [f^{(10)^2}(x)]^{1/21} [n]^{-20/21}$$

3.8 Summarization

r	d	a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d	Constraints	$O(b^r)$
2	2	$a_1 = 1.1667, a_2 = -0.0833$	$A_1 = 1, A_3 = 0.5$	$O(b^2)$
	3	$a_1 = -0.6355, a_2 = 1.3584, a_3 = -0.3604$		
	4	$a_1 = 0.3898, a_2 = -1.5648, a_3 = 2.2480, a_4 = -0.7510$		
4	3	$a_1 = 1.5208, a_2 = -0.3167, a_3 = 0.0375$	$A_1 = 1, A_3 = 0, A_5 = 0.5$	$O(b^4)$
	4	$a_1 = -0.7091, a_2 = 1.9132, a_3 = -0.9182, a_4 = 0.1593$		
	5	$a_1 = 0.4176, a_2 = -1.9654, a_3 = 3.6927, a_4 = -2.2146, a_5 = 0.4587$		
6	4	$a_1 = 1.5986, a_2 = -0.3986, a_3 = 0.0756, a_4 = -0.0070$	$A_1 = 1, A_3 = 0, A_5 = 0, A_7 = 0.5$	$O(b^6)$
	5	$a_1 = -0.7298, a_2 = 2.2624, a_3 = -1.4212, a_4 = 0.4365, a_5 = -0.0554$		
	6	$a_1 = 0.4258, a_2 = -2.2227, a_3 = 4.9473, a_4 = -4.0029, a_5 = 1.5064, a_6 = -0.2238$		
8	5	$a_1 = 1.6667, a_2 = -0.4763, a_3 = 0.1191, a_4 = -0.0199, a_5 = 0.0016$	$A_1 = 1, A_3 = 0, A_5 = 0, A_7 = 0, A_9 = 0.5$	$O(b^8)$
	6	$a_1 = -0.7445, a_2 = 2.5377, a_3 = -1.8902, a_4 = 0.7839, a_5 = -0.1811, a_6 = -0.0183$		
	7	$a_1 = 0.4290, a_2 = -2.4132, a_3 = 6.0559, a_4 = -5.9421, a_5 = 3.0752, a_6 = -0.8434, a_7 = 0.0975$		
10	6	$a_1 = 1.7143, a_2 = -0.5357, a_3 = 0.1587, a_4 = -0.0357, a_5 = 0.0052, a_6 = -0.0004$	$A_1 = 1, A_3 = 0, A_5 = 0, A_7 = 0, A_9 = 0, A_{11} = 0.5$	$O(b^{10})$
	7	$a_1 = -0.7546, a_2 = 2.7562, a_3 = -2.3102, a_4 = 1.1613, a_5 = -0.3689, a_6 = 0.0687, a_7 = -0.0058$		
	8	$a_1 = 0.4149, a_2 = -2.5013, a_3 = 6.9279, a_4 = -7.8105, a_5 = 4.9805, a_6 = -1.9036, a_7 = 0.4107, a_8 = -0.0388$		

Table (3.1): Convergence rate of bias for the proposed estimator and the values of weights for different values of r and d .

Note that: $A_l = \sum_{j=1}^d j^l a_j$.

r	d	QQ_r	$S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)$	VV_r	TT_r
2	2	0.2500	0.3185	1.0496	0.3793
	3		0.1722	0.9281	0.2319
	4		0.1126	0.8526	0.1651
4	3	0.0625	0.3939	1.3252	0.3344
	4		0.2088	1.2350	0.1902
	5		0.1403	1.1816	0.1336
6	4	0.0104	0.4064	1.5556	0.2831
	5		0.2265	1.4871	0.1650
	6		0.1570	1.4458	0.1177
8	5	0.0013	0.4171	1.7631	0.2514
	6		0.2385	1.7061	0.1485
	7		0.1680	1.6776	0.1073
10	6	0.00013	0.4243	1.9514	0.2283
	7		0.2471	1.9018	0.1364
	8		0.1775	1.8721	0.0996

Table (3.2): The values of r , d and the corresponding values of QQ_r , $S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)$, TT_r and VV_r .

Note that:

$$QQ_r = \frac{\mu_r(K)A_{r+1}}{r!}, \quad S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(u) du \sum_{j=1}^d j a_j^2 + 2 \sum_{j < l} \sum a_j a_l \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K \left[\frac{u}{j} \right] K \left[\frac{u}{l} \right] du$$

$$VV_r = \left[\frac{(r!)^2 S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)}{(2r) \mu_r^2(K) A_{r+1}^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}, \quad TT_r = \frac{2r+1}{\{2r\}^{2r/(2r+1)} \{r!\}^{2/(2r+1)}} [S(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d)]^{\frac{2r}{2r+1}} [\mu_r^2(k) A_{r+1}^2]^{\frac{1}{2r+1}}$$

and $A_{r+1} = 0.5$ for $r = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Introduction

On the basis of the previous two chapters, the mathematical properties of the proposed estimator have proved more efficient estimator than higher order kernel estimator.

In this chapter we mention to the conclusions of this study, as well as suggest further research.

4.2 Concluding Remarks

In this section we need to make a mathematical comparison by comparing $MSE\hat{f}^*(x)$ with $MSE_r^{(d)}$, where $r= 2, 4, 6, 8,$ and $10,$ and three different values of d used in Table (3.1). Moreover, we compare h^* with $b_r^{(d)}$. And the results appear in the following point :

I. If $r = 2$ and $d = 2,3,4.$ then

By comparing $MSE(\hat{f}^*(x)), MSE_2^{(2)}, MSE_2^{(3)}$ and $MSE_2^{(4)}$ we see that

$$\text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))=1.1974\text{MSE}_2^{(2)}=1.9586\text{MSE}_2^{(3)}=2.751\text{MSE}_2^{(4)} \quad (4.1)$$

Also, it follows from the formulas of h^* , $b_2^{(2)}$, $b_2^{(3)}$ and $b_2^{(4)}$ in the previous chapter that the bandwidth of the different estimator are related such that

$$h^*=0.7397b_2^{(2)}=0.8365b_2^{(3)}=0.9106b_2^{(4)} \quad (4.2)$$

II. If $r = 4$ and $d = 3,4,5$. then

By comparing $\text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))$, $\text{MSE}_4^{(3)}$, $\text{MSE}_4^{(4)}$ and $\text{MSE}_4^{(5)}$ we see that

$$\text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))=1.1974\text{MSE}_4^{(3)}=1.9586\text{MSE}_4^{(4)}=2.751\text{MSE}_4^{(5)} \quad (4.3)$$

Also, it follows from h^* , $b_4^{(3)}$, $b_4^{(4)}$ and $b_4^{(5)}$ that the bandwidth of the different estimator are related such that

$$h^*=0.7397b_4^{(3)}=0.8365b_4^{(4)}=0.9106b_4^{(5)} \quad (4.4)$$

III. If $r = 6$ and $d = 4,5,6$. then

By comparing $\text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))$, $\text{MSE}_6^{(4)}$, $\text{MSE}_6^{(5)}$ and $\text{MSE}_6^{(6)}$ we see that

$$\text{MSE}(\hat{f}^*(x))=1.6524\text{MSE}_6^{(4)}=2.8351\text{MSE}_6^{(5)}=3.974\text{MSE}_6^{(6)} \quad (4.5)$$

Also, it follows from h^* , $b_6^{(4)}$, $b_6^{(5)}$ and $b_6^{(6)}$ that the bandwidth of the different estimator are related such that

$$h^*=0.9282b_6^{(4)}=0.7917b_6^{(5)}=0.9995b_6^{(6)} \quad (4.6)$$

IV. If $r = 8$ and $d = 5,6,7$. then

By comparing $MSE(\hat{f}^*(x)), MSE_8^{(5)}, MSE_8^{(6)}$ and $MSE_8^{(7)}$ we see that

$$MSE(\hat{f}^*(x))=1.8794MSE_8^{(5)}=3.1818MSE_8^{(6)}=4.403MSE_8^{(7)} \quad (4.7)$$

Also, it follows from $h^*, b_8^{(5)}, b_8^{(6)}$ and $b_8^{(7)}$ that the bandwidth of the different estimator are related such that

$$h^*=0.9538b_8^{(5)}=0.9857b_8^{(6)}=1.002b_8^{(7)} \quad (4.8)$$

V. If $r = 10$ and $d = 6,7,8$. then

By comparing $MSE(\hat{f}^*(x)), MSE_{10}^{(6)}, MSE_{10}^{(7)}$ and $MSE_{10}^{(8)}$ we see that

$$MSE(\hat{f}^*(x))=2.086MSE_{10}^{(6)}=3.490MSE_{10}^{(7)}=4.780MSE_{10}^{(8)} \quad (4.9)$$

Also, it follows from $h^*, b_{10}^{(6)}, b_{10}^{(7)}$ and $b_{10}^{(8)}$ that the bandwidth of the different estimator are related such that

$$h^*=0.9679b_{10}^{(6)}=0.9932b_{10}^{(7)}=1.008b_{10}^{(8)} \quad (4.10)$$

From the previous formulas 4.1, 4.3, 4.5, 4.7 and 4.9 we observe a decreasing of the value of MSE of the proposed estimator when the value of d increased. Also,

the Formula 4.1 ,4.3,4.5,4.7 and 4.9 valid if we use the Formula 4.2,4.4,4.6,4.8 and 4.10 respectively .

4.3 suggestions for further research

How is the performance of the proposed estimator $\tilde{f}(x)$ compared to the classical kernel estimator $\hat{f}(x)$ and the higher order kernel estimator $\hat{f}^*(x)$ for finite sample .

In this case a simulation study is needed to be addressed . Marron and Wand (1992) gave different normal mixture densities ,which commonly used to study the nonparametric estimator for the probability density function $f(x)$. the Marron and Wand's densities represent symmetric ,kurtosis, unimodal ,bimodal ,trimodal, skewed, and strongly skewed distribution. These density can be used to study and to compare the finite sample properties of the estimator $\tilde{f}(x)$, $\hat{f}(x)$ and $\hat{f}^*(x)$ in the future research . In addition ,the value of $A_{r+1} = \lambda$ is fixed at 0.5 in this thesis . A possible future work can be adopted to study the influence of choosing λ on the performance of $\tilde{f}(x)$.

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